

NATURAL LANGUAGE EFFECTS ON PARTNER COMMUNICATION IN A PAIR PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENT: A QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This paper presents an empirical study on the impact of programming experience, sender-receiver roles, and role switching on sentiments and conversation during pair programming. The study was conducted with three groups of participants, with different levels of programming experience and using the Java programming language. The results showed that the number of times switching roles between sender and receiver in communication affected their sentiments in the direction of away from neutral sentiments that could be either positive or negative sentiments. However, the results also indicated that there is no correlation between programming experience and conversation sentiment. Moreover, the direction of sentiment could not be guaranteed by communication roles. Additionally, this research contributes to the study of natural language description by analyzing the effects of role switching, different communication roles, and programming experience on the language used during the pair programming technique.

Keywords: natural language, pair programming, communication, sentiment analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural Language Description is a rapidly growing study area that seeks to understand how humans use language to describe and convey information. This field has different applications in various domains, including natural language processing, machine translation, and others. The aim of this study is to contribute to the field of Natural Language Description by analysing emotions and find out possible correlations between various factors.

To follow this, we focused one of the use cases for the development of NLP which is sentiment analysis. Sentiment Analysis deals with the identification and classification of emotions, opinions, and attitudes which are expressed in text. The main goal of this analysis is to determine the polarity of the text, that is whether it expresses a positive, negative, or neutral sentiment [1].

Pair programming is a software development technique where two developers work together on a single task, sharing a single keyboard and mouse and taking turns in writing code and providing feedback [2]. Despite the benefits of pair programming, such as productivity and improved code quality, only a little research has been conducted to understand the natural language effects on partner communication while using pair programming.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of programming experience, sender-receiver roles, and role switching on sentiments and conversation during pair programming. The study was carried out with three groups of individuals, who had varying levels of programming experience and used the Java programming language during the experiment. The results of

this research are significant as they provide a comprehensive insight into the influence of natural language on communication between pair programming partners which can be used both for improvement of the effectiveness of the software development technique and to contribute to the generation of more accurate and nuanced natural language descriptions.

The study was conducted as a between-subject research design, with participants completing programming tasks in pairs, while their conversations were recorded and analyzed. The collected data were analyzed in order to assess the impact of programming experience, sender-receiver roles, and role switching on sentiments and conversation during pair programming

The structure of paper is divided into several sections and subsections. The Introduction section provides an overview of our study and research topic. Research Objective presents subsections namely: Hypotheses, Independent Variables, and Dependent Variables. The Study Design section consists of Confounding Factors, Participants, Survey, Material Creation, and Task. The Data Analysis Procedure section which describes the methods, and tools, are used for analyzing the collected data. The Results section presented the collected data, with a focus on the two subsections which are Presentation of the Collected Data and Descriptive Statistics. The Discussion section provides a discussion over the research question, and hypotheses. The Further Insights section provides additional findings and insights into the experiment result, and the Threats to Validity section discusses potential limitations and biases in the study. The Related Work section presents previous studies and literature related to this study. Finally, in the Conclusion and Future Work section, we have

summarized the main findings, implications of the research, and potential areas of improvement in the future.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

There is a narrow, even fewer approach and articles regarding the natural language effects on communication between partners who do pair programming. This research paper aims to do qualitative analysis to reveal how sentiments change and correlate with programming experiences and role-switching (sender and receiver) during conversations between partners. We want to find correlations which can be helpful in future works to develop natural language.

For structured analysis, the following research question should be answered:

RQ: How does natural language affect sender-receiver communication pattern in terms of partner sentiments during pair programming between experienced and novice programmers?

A. Hypotheses

In terms of our research, it may have correlations between pairs' sentiments and different dimensions of pair programming (developer experience and roles), which can yield future development of natural language.

1) Programming experience

H1₀: *Experienced programmers show more positive sentiments than novices sentiments.*

H1₁: *Experienced programmers do not consistently show more positive sentiments than novices sentiments.*

According to our research, pair programming allowed for talks between developers. These contained explanations of general knowledge of software development and system-specific knowledge [3]. Thus, the sentiments of these dialogues might be positive, especially, when experienced developers' impart knowledge to novices. Additionally, experienced programmers' sentiments could also be more positive than novices' sentiments. In contrast, novices do interpretations regarding experienced programmers' explanations. Curiosity can cause more positive sentiments in novices [4]. This may lead to experienced programmers' sentiments not consistently showing more positive than novices' sentiments as a result.

2) Roles switching

H2₀: *Partners who switched roles more are not near neutral sentiments or do not have neutral sentiments.*

H2₁: *Partners who switched roles more are near neutral sentiments than those who switch roles less.*

Regarding our null hypothesis, switching roles may not affect pairs' sentiments. Meaning that changing roles may not reveal more neutral sentiments or even not have neutral emotions between partners.

However, during pair programming, changing roles is the behavior that may also significantly influence partners' sentiments. They share an understanding to arrive at the final code [5]. They attempt to transfer relatively to their roles their coding ideas, knowledge, and concepts for each idea. Therefore, depending on how many times the roles are switched between partners, this may significantly contribute to more near-

neutral sentiments than other pairs in which one switched roles less.

3) Individuals' roles

H3₀: *Receiver sentiments express more negative than sender sentiments.*

H3₁: *Receiver sentiments do not consistently express more negative than sender sentiments.*

Sentimental transmissions from one side to another during communication between pairs may also be affected by individuals' roles as well as programming experience and switching roles in between.

From the study, in email communication, the receivers interpret the sender's sentiment based on the received statement. Whereas senders demonstrate sentiment states, receivers judge the senders' emotions by themselves [6]. Therefore, receivers may express their sentiments more negatively than the receivers'. On the other hand, in their experiment, Y. Kato et al. reported that the emotional states that the sender gives and interprets by the receiver also correlate with the sender's emotional expectations [6]. The emotional interpretation of the receiver may not cause negative sentiments in comparison with the senders'.

B: Independent Variables:

This research has two independent variables: partners' roles (sender and receiver) during communication and participants' programming experience (novice and experienced programmers).

C: Dependent Variables:

To assess how the programming experience and roles of the sender-receiver communication model affect communication between pairs, we evaluate different sentiments, such as neutral, positive, and negative.

III. STUDY DESIGN

The aim of our experiment is to analyze conversations of pairs with different experiences working on programming tasks. We will spread a survey to find voluntary participants and conduct an online workshop to encourage participants to solve Java tasks using pair programming techniques. Our experiment is considered a between-subject research design. We will qualitatively analyze their communication in terms of sentiments they have used by recording their conversation and observe different correlations between their emotions, experiences, and roles. We will not inform participants that we will analyze their conversation to avoid confounding factors [7], such as they can imitate during the conversation.

In the next step, we plan to transcribe recordings and analyze them using sentiment analysis [8]. The recording collection will allow us to evaluate how pairs' sentiments correlated with their experiences and roles as sender and receiver. By analyzing recordings, we will extract how many times sender and receiver roles have switched between partners, which sentiments occur individually in the conversation of receivers and senders, and how the conversation affects partners' sentiments within the group after changing roles between receivers and senders.

A. Confounding Factors

Confounding factors resulted in the difference in research experiment outcomes that occur because of biased research participants selection in each research

group. This study relates to communication between experienced and novice programmers during pair programming. To avoid between-group bias, communication ability, programming, and problem-solving skills are serious factors. Accordingly, age, gender, educational background, and programming experience are considered confounding variables in this study in which all volunteers are qualified before being admitted to the experiment. All participants in the 24-30 age range are chosen for both males and females as well as undergraduate and graduate students in computing-related fields for educational backgrounds, including Automotive Software Engineering, Computer Engineering, and Computer Science at Technische Universität Chemnitz. In terms of programming experience, participants who have less than a year of programming experience are considered a novice. Otherwise, participants are treated as experienced programmers during research experiments.

B. Participants

Participants are recruited from the Faculty of Computer Science at Technische Universität Chemnitz (TU Chemnitz) through an online survey. We recruit participants from Technische Universität Chemnitz (TU Chemnitz). We have prepared an online survey to select suitable voluntary participants for our experiment. We expect three novice and three experienced programmers to build 3 groups in total. Participants will have insights into the Java programming language. To avoid confounding factors, we keep similar age groups (between 24-30 years old), mixed gender, and similar programming experiences between each group.

There can be participants, both graduate, and undergraduate students. With this survey, we will also gather the demographics of the participants. Due to time limits, we recruit participants who have already worked with Visual Studio Code (VSCode) and ask them to choose one of the available time slots for the workshop. After completing the survey, to avoid confounding variables, we try to match participants by considering their experiences and defining participants. We would also form groups equally, with one experienced and one novice as partners. All participants offered a 10-Euro Amazon gift card after completing our workshop.

Participants hired via E-mail. The experiment began with 10 participants, of which 6 were able to complete the workshop successfully. Each group was given three tasks of different categories. However, technical challenges prevented four out of ten participants from fully participating in the workshop.

Volunteers are qualified and matched to a suitable partner as shown in Table I. In Group 1, a 29-year-old female programmer with more than 3 years of programming experience is considered an experienced programmer and is matched to a 27-year-old male novice programmer who has less than 1 year of programming experience, while Group 2 is 24-year-old male pair which an experience one is studying at the graduate level in Web Engineering and a novice is studying at undergraduate level in Computer Engineering. Lastly, Group 3, an over 3-year experienced programmer who is studying Automotive Software Engineering is matched with a less-than-1-year experienced programmer who is studying Web Engineering. However, both of them are female and stay at the graduate level.

Table I

Participants' Characteristics and Matched Pairs in the Study

No	Group	Roles in Group	Education	Age	Gender	Major of Study	Year of Prog. Exp.
1	1	experienced programmer	Graduate	29	Female	Web Engineering	Over 3 years
2	1	novice programmer	Graduate	27	Male	Web Engineering	0-1 year
3	2	experienced programmer	Graduate	24	Male	Web Engineering	1-3 year
4	2	novice programmer	Undergraduate	24	Male	Computer Engineering	0-1 year
5	3	experienced programmer	Graduate	30	Female	Automotive Software Engineering	Over 3 years
6	3	novice programmer	Graduate	24	Female	Web Engineering	0-1 year

Besides, it shows the education levels of the participants who took part in the survey. The table outlines that out of 6 total participants, only 1 participant was an undergraduate student, accounting for 16.67% of the participants. The remaining, 5 out of 6, equals 83.33% of the participants who are graduate students. The data gives an understanding of the educational background of the survey participants and helps us to understand the demographics of the group which we have studied, even though we choose mostly undergraduate students.

Additionally, in terms of the majors of the participants in this study, the majority of participants are Master of Web Engineering students, 4 out of 6 participants amounting to 66.67%. Meanwhile, another 2 participants, each of them consisting of students with a major in Computer Engineering and Automotive Software Engineering. The table provides an understanding of

the academic background of the participant and the fields they come from.

C. Survey

In this section, we will describe our survey that we used to collect information about volunteers and find potential participants for this study. The Survey was created using Google Forms and was distributed to students at Technische Universität Chemnitz via a digital poster that included a barcode linking to the survey. The survey consisted of several questions aimed at gathering information about the participant's background and experience with programming, as well as their availability for the workshop days.

We have designed survey to start by asking for the participants' name, surname, birthdate, and gender. Afterwards we asked about their education level (graduate or undergraduate) and major of study. Next, questions

was about their programming experience, including how many projects they had worked on and which programming languages they preferred to use. Participants were also asked if they had experience with pair programming techniques and which integrated development environments they have used such as MS Visual Studio Code, IntelliJ, and MS Visual Studio. Additionally, participants were asked about their operating system and available time slots for the workshop days. Finally, we asked for additional contact information and required from participants to give their consent for screen and voice recording during the workshop.

After the survey was completed, the collected data were analyzed in order to choose participants for the study. Measures were taken to eliminate any confounding variables, for example by selecting participants who had prior experience with Visual Studio Code and used

Windows operating systems. The sample consisted of a balance of both experienced and novice programmers, with 5 of each. The majority of the participants preferred the workshop to take place on the 2nd of January, and the study was conducted over the 3 days. Additionally, the majority of the chosen participants were familiar with the Java programming language and fell within the age range of 24-30.

In Fig. 1, represented the results of a survey that was conducted and we have visualized responses in a pie chart. Out of 37 total responses, 28 volunteers which were the percentage 75.68% were male, while 24.32% - 9 of them were female. This information provides an overview of the gender distribution of the survey participants and highlights the relative proportion of males and females who filled out the survey.

Percentage of Volunteer by Gender

Fig. 1: Distribution of Volunteers by Gender in the Hiring Workshop Survey

Fig. 2, a pie chart shows the volunteers' education ratio of 37 responses that approximately 84%, 31 volunteers, are graduate students whereas roughly 16%,

amounting to 6 people, are undergraduate students. This information reveals that the majority of volunteers are graduate students.

Percentage of Volunteer by Education

Fig. 2: Volunteer Education Ratio

The candidates who are interested in participating in our experiment are studying in various majors. Using Fig. 3, the largest proportion of them is Web Engineering which takes 13.51% - 5 people followed by Computer Engineering, Computer Science, Information Technology, and Engineering amounting to 10.81%,

10.81%, 10.81%, and 8.11% respectively. The other proportions share the same amount of 2.7% or 1 student such as Business, Chemical Engineering, Construction Management, Mathematics, and others. This can deduce that our experiment is attractive in the diversity of study areas.

Percentage of Volunteer by Major of Study

Fig. 3: Participants Proportions of Majors of Interested in the Experiment

The percentage of volunteers by year of programming experience is demonstrated in Fig. 4. About 41% of volunteers, 15 out of 37 people, have 1-3 years of programming experience. Equally, another 41% of can-

didates have more than 3 years of programming experience. Lastly, the residual part takes 18.92%, 7 people, indicating 0-1 year programming experience participants.

Percentage of Volunteer by Year of Programming Experience

Fig. 4: Pie Chart of Volunteers' Programming Experience

In conclusion, this survey ensured that a diverse and representative group of participants were chosen for the study and that confounding factors were minimized.

D. Material Creation

We designed a survey in order to reach the right participants for our experiment. We have asked questions on different categories such as education and programming experience. After completion of the survey, to find voluntary participants regarding chosen time slots, we will define the workshop day which is planned to be conducted in the first week of January 2023.

On workshop day, pairs will be provided with introductory materials about pair programming techniques, Test-Driven Development (TDD) methodology, and instructions for how they can use Visual Studio Code (VSCode) with Live Share extension to be able to work with pair programming. Then, we will give participants 1 hour to solve 3 different types of Java programming language tasks which will be on the same difficulty levels from Codewars.com [9] [10]. This website is a developer community sharing the problems which all developers practice and challenge their programming skills in various programming languages. The problems on this website are divided into 8 levels, the easiest one is 8 kyu and the hardest one is 1 kyu. In order to examine different situations between pairs

which will consist of experienced and novice programmers, we have designed tasks at the same levels, but on different topics. As our participant groups consist of 1 experienced and 1 novice programmer, we only select the famous verified 6 kyu level ones for those 3 workshop tasks. Because the experienced ones may solo complete 8 kyu and 7 kyu problems by themselves. Participants should use pair programming techniques during solving tasks in a group and also may or may not use test-driven development iterative methodology which embraces them knowing when they should swap their roles.

We also considered the possibility of the learning experience of participants during the workshop with the same task topics and choosing different ones. One task is about converting string to camel case whereas another task is about fundamental algorithms and the last task is related to arrays. And, we will see how they behave while solving the tasks, especially, after they have experience from the previous tasks.

All pairs invited to the online meetings, Zoom, on the workshop day. Each pair broken into separate rooms and they worked as a group. After completion of workshops, participants asked to put their codes into Google Drive. During the workshop, we record screen and audio. We store and transcribe the recordings so that we can study their dialogue. All the information participants provide is treated as confidential and only

be used for our research. They can request deletion at any time beforehand. Collected data will not be shared with anyone not involved in this study. In a possible publication of the result of this survey and workshop, the data will be anonymous.

E. Task

In order to observe the impact of pair programming on sentiments, programming experiences, and the role of the sender-receiver during the collaboration, three tasks were assigned to the participants during the workshop. These tasks were designed to test the participants' understanding of programming concepts and their ability to collaborate effectively. The tasks were as follows:

Task 1: Convert dash/underscore delimited words into camel casing. The first word within the output should be capitalized only if the original word was capitalized (known as Upper Camel Case, also often referred to as Pascal case). The next words should always be capitalized [10].

Task 2: Write a function, persistence, that takes in a positive parameter number and returns its multiplicative persistence, which is the number of times you must multiply the digits in number until you reach a single digit [10].

Task 3: Given an array of integers, find an index N where the sum of the integers to the left of N is equal to the sum of the integers to the right of N. If there is no index that would make this happen, return -1 [10].

We created separate folders for each group in Google Drive and provided each group with a unique link to access their respective folder. This allowed each group to upload their task solutions, as well as access the materials (such as instructions for the tasks, examples, and any necessary resources) provided for each task. This helped to streamline the process of collecting and evaluating the task solutions and results. The results of the tasks were analyzed to determine the impact of pair programming on sentiments, programming experiences, and the role of the sender-receiver during the collaboration.

During the workshop, we allocated specific time slots for each task. For Task 1 and Task 2, participants were given 15 minutes each to complete the task. Task 3 was given a longer time slot of 25 minutes. Participants were required to complete the tasks within the allocated time frame, and no additional time was given. This was done to simulate a real-world scenario where time constraints are often a factor in completing tasks. Additionally, the limited time frame also helped to assess the participants' ability to work under pressure and manage their time effectively.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

After successful completion of the workshop, we have followed several procedures in this study to analyze the data collected. We transcribed all 3 sessions of 6 participants and performed our analysis based on text material. To achieve the goals of our study, we utilized a range of tools, technologies, and techniques. For example, we used Microsoft Word to transcribe the data, Google Natural Language AI for sentiment analysis, JupyterNotebook for processing files, and Microsoft Power BI for visualizing and summarizing the data in different forms. The steps and procedures of this study include the following:

1) Transcription: Source data is screen recordings with paired programmers' conversation voices. Transcription is needed to convert our data for further analysis. Microsoft Word [11] is used to transcribe all 3 group conversations.

2) Correction: Albeit reliable automation tools, mistakes still occur in the transcription process. Manual correction is applied for higher accuracy.

3) Complementation: Plain text is produced from the previous steps. Defining the speaker's name for each sentence is the responsibility of humans. Moreover, the interpretation of each sentence is handled manually to identify sender-receiver roles based on the Shannon-Weaver Model of Communication. The model states that communication consists of the sender, message, encoder, channel with noise, decoder, receiver, and feedback [12]. The cycle of communication shows in Fig.5.

Fig. 5: Shannon-Weaver Model of Communication [12]

As a result of this step, sender and receiver roles are marked to speakers and sentences. Afterwards, changing roles can immediately actuate by comparing with their previous roles. In other words, in the case that a sender receives a message and answers back followed by a new question which unrelated to the question, we count this situation as a 1-time changing role. Otherwise, a question that is related to a sender question is not defined as role-changed, but feedback by question

instead, and also does not count as a changing role because the sender's question is still open.

4) Execution: Sentiment analysis is a natural language processing (NLP) aiming to extract emotion from input text [13]. Regarding a trusted provider, Google, we selected Google NLP named Google Natural Language AI [14] to determine our data. Notwithstanding, in order to effectively analyze data, we have

to perform a cleansing of data then followed by an operation process as follows.

a) Pre-processing: In NLP, it recognizes that text will be analyzed by sentence. But, our data is real-life conversation. Many times, humans continue speaking long sentences, especially when implementing programs, for example, "we can add a data type and we can declare a function... and.. and... and...". On that occasion, adding proper sentence ending punctuations is significant. Then we manually determine suitable positions and punctuations including a period (.), question mark, and exclamation point [15].

b) Processing: With cleaned conversation text, requests are separately made to Google Natural Language AI by the dimension of our analysis aspect comprising the whole conversation, speakers, senders, and receivers, in each workshop using Listing 1. JSON format will be responded from the endpoint.


```

{
  "documentSentiment": {
    "magnitude": 147.4,
    "score": 0
  },
  "language": "en",
  "sentences": [
    {
      "text": {
        "content": "You and me.",
        "beginOffset": 0
      },
      "sentiment": {
        "magnitude": 0,
        "score": 0
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

```

group,seq,dimension,content,score,magnitude
1,1,experience,You and me.,0,0
1,2,experience,"uh what is your name Tmusal
1,3,experience,OK.,0.5,0.5
1,4,experience,Thank you.,0.8,0.8
1,5,experience,"as far as I know , uh you a
1,6,experience,OK.,0.5,0.5
1,7,experience,"so, for today, we will be a
1,8,experience,let me share my screen.,-0.3
1,9,experience,OK.,0.5,0.5
1,10,experience,"so, let's just get started
1,11,experience,"With uh I am a driver and
1,12,experience,OK.,0.5,0.5
1,13,experience,let me check it out.,-0.2,0
1,14,experience,I'm not sure.,-0.1,0.1
1,15,experience,OK.,0.5,0.5
1,16,experience,I already encouraged and Li

```

Fig. 6: Sentiment Analysis Results in CSV Format, Transformed from JSON Using JupyterNotebook [16]

6) Visualization:

All charts are created by Microsoft Power BI [17] which is a powerful visualization tool allowing us both to manipulate data and create astonishing visualizations.

As a result of the processed data, the communication between paired programmers is promptly visualized. Then we can figure out insight for our hypotheses and the research question, for example, Fig. 7 is describing a data visualization that shows three columns: speakers (A and B), conversation, and score for each of them. The conversation column includes sentences that we have extracted from workshop recordings and the

```

curl -X POST \
-H "Content-Type: application/json; charset=utf-8" \
--data "{
'encodingType': 'UTF8',
'document': {
'type': 'PLAIN_TEXT',
'language': 'en',
'content': 'OK, let's start with the first task!'
}
}" "https://language.googleapis.com/v1/documents:analyzeSentiment?key=[api-key]"

```

Listing 1: A Curl Post request to Google Natural Language AI

5) Transformation: Sentiment analysis results are responded in JSON. The transformation from JSON into CSV has been done using JupyterNotebook [16]. The result is shown in Fig. 6.

score column includes the sentiment scores of each sentence. The example presented a conversation between two speakers, where the first sentence by speaker A has a positive sentiment score of 0.50, and the second sentence of this participant has a neutral sentiment score of 0.00. The third and fourth sentences have negative sentiment scores of -0.30 and -0.40 respectively. Additionally, sender and receiver roles have been defined at the end of rows indicating what is the current role of that sentence. With the first row, speaker A is a receiver. Then (s)he starts new content and questions in the 2nd - 4th row. In this circumstance, we counted as a 1-time changing role.

Fig. 7: Sentiment Analysis Results of Speakers' Sentences, Showing Role Changes and Sentiment Scores for Each Sentence

V. RESULTS

In this section, we present the findings of our sentiment analysis. To evaluate the sentiment, different dimensions were used for data analysis: groups, different roles, and programmers with different experiences.

Our analysis of the transcriptions revealed insights that helped formulate answers related to this study's hypotheses. In total, we spent 30 hours analyzing our data. The tasks are shown in Table II.

Table II

Data Analysis Task Details in Research

No.	Time Spent (hrs)	Tasks
1	4	transcribes process by Microsoft Words
2	8	corrects transcribed scripts
3	4	defines speakers and sender-receiver
4	4	adds proper sentence ending punctuations
5	3	requests for sentiment analysis by Google Natural Language AI API
6	3	transforms sentiment analysis results from JSON into CSV using JupyterNotebook
7	4	visualizes results by Microsoft Power BI
Total	30	

A. Presentation of the Collected Data

In this part, we will provide an overview of the data that we have collected and describe the format in which it will be presented for qualitative analysis.

We organized and distributed the data based on factors such as programming experience, communication roles, and group. To reveal comparisons between groups and individuals, we have used tables, bar graphs, and text as methods for presenting our findings.

Table III, for example, shows extracted sentences from the workshop transcription, illustrating the different types of sentiment, namely positive, negative, and

neutral, referred to as polarity. Additionally, the table presents the sentiment score of the polarity of each sentence. Using Google API, sentences have been scored from -1 to 1, less than 0 indicates negative sentiment, 0 means neutral, and above 0 is positive sentiment. For instance, "Yeah, we can do it." has been determined to a 0.5 score which implies moderately positive sentiment whereas "I pressed enter, but it is not recognized." has been evaluated with a -0.9 score indicating strongly negative sentiment.

Table III

Sentences and Their Corresponding Sentiment Scores for Each Polarity (Positive, Neutral, and Negative)

Sentences	Score	Sentiment
Yeah, we can do it.	0.5	Positive
Let's understand how to set the environment.	0.0	Neutral
I pressed enter but it is not recognized.	-0.9	Negative

Table IV presents data on different groups of participants, organized by their programming experience, roles during conversations, and average scores for the whole conversation. The group column represents the group number in which 2 participants are divided. Roles during conversation represent the role of participants during conversation divided into Receiver and Sender. Decimal numbers represent the scores, positive

numbers (0 - 1.0] indicate a positive sentiment, negative numbers indicate a negative sentiment [-1.0 - 0), and zero indicates neutral sentiment [0.0]. For example, Group 1 has a 0.06 score for experienced participants, which is positive polarity, a -0.04 score for novice participants is a negative one, a 0.01 score for a receiver, a 0.03 score for a sender who both represents positive sentiments, and an overall score of 0.02 for the whole conversation is also evaluated as positive sentiment.

Table IV

Sentiment Scores of Sender, Receiver, Experienced, and Novice programmers by Groups

Group	Programming experience		Roles during conversation		Whole conversation
	Experienced	Novice	Receiver	Sender	
Group 1	0.06	-0.04	0.01	0.03	0.02
Group 2	0.09	0.17	0.19	0.07	0.12
Group 3	-0.03	-0.05	-0.02	-0.05	-0.04

In Fig. 8, the number of sentiments during conversation is calculated in percentage by group. For each bar, three sentiment percentages are stacked, including negative, neutral, and positive sentiment. For example, Group 1 has 44.13% of a negative element while neutral and positive ones present 18.26% and 37.61%, respectively.

On another aspect, the elements' size of each group can be compared to the other groups due to the same sequence stacks. The collected data show that all groups conducted approximately 37%-44% negative sentiment, 16%-25% neutral sentiment, and 32%-47% positive sentiment.

Fig. 8: Percentage of Sentiments by Group

In conclusion, we have presented the collected data in various ways to provide an understanding of the sentiment analysis results. Overall, the data we have provided insight into the sentiment scores of experienced and novice programmers, the impact of role switching on sentiment, and the sentiment scores of senders and receivers. The data support the study's hypotheses and serve as the foundation for our analysis and conclusion in the following section of this study.

B. Descriptive Statistics

In this section, we will be evaluating the results of our study in relation to our hypotheses. By analyzing the descriptive statistics of the data collected, we aim to identify patterns and correlations within the data and determine whether or not our hypotheses are supported by evidence. This will allow us to gain a deeper understanding of the impact of natural language on communication patterns and sentiments during pair programming between experienced and novice programmers.

1) Programming experience

In Fig. 9 bar graph is showing the average sentiment scores of experienced and novice programmers in three different groups. The x-axis of the graph displays the different groups and the distinction between experienced and novice programmers, while the y-axis shows the average score of sentiment. In Group 1, the sentiment score for experienced programmers is 0.06, which is positive, and the sentiment score for novice programmers is -0.04, which is negative.

In Group 2, the sentiment score for experienced programmers is 0.09, which is positive, and the sentiment score for novice programmers is 0.17, which is positive as well. In Group 3, the sentiment score for experienced programmers is -0.03, which is negative, and the sentiment score for novice programmers is -0.05, which is also negative.

Fig. 9: Comparison of Average Sentiment Scores for Experienced and Novice Programmers in Group 1, 2, and 3.

Also, Fig. 10 illustrated as a bar graph suggest that the average sentiment scores for only positive sentiments during the whole conversation were relatively similar across all groups and experience levels, with Group 1 experienced having a score of 0.46, novice having a score of 0.45, Group 2 experienced having a score of 0.57, novice having a score of 0.56, and Group 3 experienced having a score of 0.40, novice having a score of 0.39. Overall, all groups, senders and receivers show no significantly different scores, a difference of only 0.1 scores.

2) Roles switching

As a result, we found that the number of switching roles between a sender and a receiver is related to the

sentiment of the conversation. Considering Table V, groups 1, 2, and 3 show average scores of conversation, 0.02, 0.12, and -0.04, respectively, while the numbers of switching roles are 21, 35, and 86 times throughout the workshop. This reveals that the number of changing roles influences the average score of participants' sentiment. The more they change positions, the more an average sentiment is away from a neutral score (0.0). Nonetheless, according to the result, groups 2 and 3 indicate positive and negative sentiments. This means that we cannot guarantee their sentiment direction, whether it is positive or negative.

Table V

Summary of Switching Roles and Average Conversation Scores by Group

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Average Score of Conversation	0.02	0.12	-0.04
Sum of switching roles	21	35	86

With Fig. 11, participants consistently demonstrate the lowest number of neutral sentiments in all groups. On the one hand, participants present more negative than positive sentiments in Group 1 and 3. On the

other hand, Group 2 indicates positive more than negative sentiment during the workshop. In a nutshell, the correlation between the number of changing roles and the number of both positive and negative sentiments is invisible.

Fig. 11: Distribution of Sentiments by Group and Role Switching

3) Individuals' roles

Fig. 12 illustrates the overall sentiment scores of senders and receivers. The x-axis represents different groups divided based on the receiver and sender roles, while the y-axis represents the average sentiment score.

During the workshop, Group 1's data shows that the receiver has a sentiment score of 0.01, and the sender has a sentiment score of 0.03, which indicates

that the sender has slightly more positive sentiment than the receiver. In the second group, the receiver has a sentiment score of 0.19, and the sender has a score of 0.07, which means that the receiver has a more positive sentiment than the sender. In Group 3, the receiver has a sentiment score of -0.02, and the sender has a sentiment score of -0.05, while both the receiver and sender have negative sentiment scores.

Fig. 12: Comparison of Average Sentiment Scores for Senders and Receivers in Group 1, 2, and 3

Also, we have considered the average score of the negative sentiments used by receivers and senders, which are visualized in Fig. 13. In Group 1, the receiver has a score of -0.36, and the sender has a score of -0.33. Similarly, in Group 2, the receiver has a score of -0.39, and the sender has a score of -0.36, a difference score

of -0.03. In Group 3, the receiver has a score of -0.41, and the sender has a score of -0.36. These results provide that the receiver and sender sentiments are relatively equal in terms of negative sentiment. On the whole results show similar differences between the receivers' and the senders' scores.

Fig. 13: Negative Sentiment Scores of Senders and Receivers by Group

VI. DISCUSSION

In this section, we will discuss the results by answering our research question, and research hypotheses. We will conclude with discussion over further questions and further insights.

A. Research Question

In this research, investigating the impacts of natural language on the communication between experienced and novice programmers is the main objective. To answer this research question, three groups of paired participants were shaped based on their programming experiences and assigned 3 different programming tasks which requirement was to use only Java programming language.

The results of the experiment, which aimed to answer the research question of "How does natural language affect sender-receiver communication patterns in terms of partner sentiments during pair programming between experienced and novice programmers?", have provided insights into the nature of communication between experienced and novice programmers during pair programming. The results showed that the sentiment expressed during pair programming is not solely determined by the experience level of the programmer. Rather, it may be due to a complex interaction between the individual characteristics of both the sender and the receiver, as well as the roles they adopt during the conversation.

One surprising finding was that experienced programmers did not always express positive sentiments. This suggests that the experience level of a programmer does not necessarily correspond with positive sentiments during pair programming. Moreover, the receivers in the experiment were not always more likely to express negative sentiments than the senders. This also contributes to highlight the importance of considering the individual characteristics of both partners in the pair, as well as the dynamics of their interaction, when assessing the sentiment expressed during pair programming.

Additionally, the results indicated that pairs with highly switched roles tend to have average sentiments far from neutral. This finding highlights the importance of considering the dynamic nature of communication during pair programming. It suggests that the sentiment expressed during pair programming depends on their

interaction and the roles they adopt during the conversation. As well, it may be supported by the individual characteristics of the partners

In conclusion, the results of this experiment suggest that natural language can affect the sender-receiver communication patterns during pair programming between experienced and novice programmers. Further research could explore the individual and situational factors that contribute to the sentiment expressed during pair programming and how these factors can be optimized to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of the pair programming process.

B. Hypotheses

1) Programming experience

Regarding the first hypothesis, data shows that experienced programmers do not consistently show more positive sentiments than novice programmers in all groups in Fig. 9. Therefore, we may conclude that the null hypothesis $H1_0$ should be rejected and $H1_1$ should be accepted instead. However, as Fig. 10 provided, the result shows that the average positive sentiment scores for experienced and novice programmers are similar across all groups, with no significant difference between the two.

Overall, these results suggest that while there may be some correlation between experience level and sentiment, it is not as straightforward as initially assumed, and other elements like group interactions, and participants' traits might also affect the sentiments. Likely, that experience level does not significantly impact the positive sentiments expressed during pair programming.

2) Roles switching

The second hypothesis's result in Fig. 11, which explored the relationship between receiver-sender roles and sentiments, was supported by our findings. We can say that the number of changing roles directly affects the average score of participants' sentiment. In other words, an increase in changing roles leads to an increase or decrease in the average sentiment score. Hence, the null hypothesis $H2_0$ can be accepted.

3) Individuals' roles

Finally for the third hypothesis, in terms of the null hypothesis, which states that receiver sentiments express more negative than sender sentiments, the results do not support this claim because of the result in Fig.

12. The data shows that in Group 2 and Group 3, the sentiment scores of the receivers are more positive than those of the senders. Contrastingly, the receiver in Group 1 shows more negative sentiment than the sender. Consequently, the alternative hypothesis, which states that receiver sentiments do not consistently express more negative than sender, is supported by the data. This resulted in a rejection of H_{30} . We may also need to do further analysis over more data which can help to draw more definitive conclusions.

VII. FURTHER INSIGHTS

Further questions that arose from this study can be: Are there other factors that may influence the sentiments of programmers during pair programming? How can we further investigate the impact of natural language on communication patterns and sentiments during pair programming? Also, it may be interesting to research how other variables, such as task complexity, may affect conversation during pair programming. It may also be valuable to explore the changes in sentiments throughout pair programming sessions and to see how communication may impact task performance.

1) Result of tasks

The results of the tasks conducted during the workshop provide valuable insights into the impact of pair programming on sentiments, programming experiences, and the role of sender-receiver during collaboration. These insights can be leveraged to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the pair programming approach in software development.

Task results can be divided into 2 aspects including task completion and task correctness. All tasks are carefully examined for completeness and are tested with 2 possible test cases provided in Codewars [10]. Table VI shows the task completion of all groups. After finishing the experiment, Task 1 was completed by Group 1 only, Task 2 was completed by Group 3 only, and Task 3 was completed by Group 1 and 2. In the other words, Group 1 and Group 3 came with 2 completed out of 3 tasks while Group 2 could not complete all provided tasks.

Table VI

Results of Task Completion By Group

Group Name	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3
Group 1	completed	not completed	completed
Group 2	not completed	not completed	not completed
Group 3	not completed	completed	completed

Moving to task correctness, with Table VII, Group 1 passed Task 1 and all groups failed for Task 2. In Task 3, Group 1 failed, Group 2 partly failed, and Group 3 passed. In the other words, Group 1 and Group 3 resulted in 1 completely correct task. Surprisingly, one of

Group 2's tasks passed 1 out of 2 test cases. This means that they produced 1 partially completed task, even though they could not complete any given tasks.

Table VII

Results of Task Correction By Group

Group Name	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3
Group 1	pass 2	fail 2	fail 2
Group 2	fail 2	fail 2	pass 1, fail 1
Group 3	fail 2	fail 2	pass 2

The average conversation score for Group 1, Group 2, and Group 3, as shown in the Summary of Switching Roles and Average Conversation Scores by Group Table (Table V) in the Result section, was 0.02, 0.12, and -0.04 respectively. The results imply that Group 1 produced near-neutral sentiment with 1 completed task. Interestingly, Group 2 showed the highest positive sentiment score with a partially completed task. And, even Group 3 showed negative sentiment, but they still came up with a successful task. Consequently, all groups show appealing outcomes and all of them tend to be diverse. Hence, research is needed to conduct in-depth to show a correlation between task completion and correctness in order to contribute the pair-programming productivity in the future.

2) Content of the conversation

Fig. 14 illustrates the count of content in the conversations of Group 1, 2, and 3. A total of 2249 sentences were analyzed and the word "OK" was used 186 times, which suggests that the participants were generally in agreement with each other during the conversations. The word "yeah" was used 81 times, indicating a sense of affirmation or agreement among the participants. The word "yes" was used 52 times, which further supports the idea of agreement among the group members. The use of "hmm" 31 times and "oh" 30 times suggests moments of contemplation or surprise during the conversations. The use of "uh" 12 times and "right" 11 times may indicate moments of hesitation or confusion. Lastly, the word "no" was used 9 times, indicating instances of disagreement or dissent among group members.

Fig. 14: Count of Conversation Content in Group 1, 2, and 3

Overall, this tree diagram provides insights into the general sentiment and dynamics of the conversations among the groups during the workshop. The use of specific words and phrases can indicate moments of agreement, disagreement, contemplation, hesitation, and surprise among partners during pair programming which means the analysis of conversation content can be used to understand the impact of natural language on group communication.

VIII. THREATS TO VALIDITY

In the context of our qualitative analysis, there are several potential threats to validity that should be considered in future studies.

A. Internal Validity

One potential threat is that participants' mood and personality traits, as well as an understanding of the workshop materials, may have affected the quality of the conversations and emotions during pair programming. These factors were not measured but could have impacted the results.

Additionally, the limited types and complexity of given tasks used in this experiment may have biased the results, leading to inaccurate conclusions about the relationship between the independent and dependent variables and can lead to biased communication sentiments.

B. External Validity

External validity refers to the generalizability of the result. In the context of our qualitative analysis, there are several potential threats to validity that should be considered in future studies.

One threat to validity is the sample size. Low population validity was shown in our because of only 6 participants, and this may not be large enough to be representative of the entire population of programmers. Similarly, low population validity was also shown in terms of participants' age range, only participants the 24-30 were admitted to this research experiment.

Java programming language was also another treat that we embraced for the experiment to research natural language on communication during pair programming. However, Java is widely used in the industrial world. Furthermore, it's strongly typed and object-oriented programming. So, it's an excellent choice for this research. Besides, the environment was similar to real-world development in that all participants were not allowed to ask anything after pair-programming sessions began, and they also were not interrupted by investigators.

IX. RELATED WORK

The impact of natural language on partners' communications in pair programming environments has received limited attention in the different literature. However, some studies have investigated the role of communication in pair programming and its effects on programming tasks.

Some studies focus on the effective communication role in the success of pair programming. For instance, researchers have investigated the impact of gender and cultural differences on communication during pair programming [18].

Additionally, studies have also shown that the use of natural language and nonverbal, play a significant role in effective communication during pair programming [19].

Another research focuses on the high level of communication during pair programming. In that study, they investigated that levels of compatibility and confidence between pairs did not positively influence the partners' conversation [5].

However, there is limited research on the impact of programming experience, sender-receiver roles, and role-switching on sentiments during conversation using the pair programming technique. This study adds to the existing knowledge by conducting a qualitative analysis of the impact of programming experience, sender-

receiver pattern on conversation, and role-switching on sentiments and conversation during pair programming.

X. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Working with a partner using a pair-programming technique relies on communication and then natural language occurs and directly affects the interlocutor's sentiment. Nonetheless, it probably additionally influences the quality of work. Regarding the widely used, experienced-novice pair is fascinating and worthwhile to investigate in order to contribute their natural language.

The results of this experiment reveal that experienced and novice programmers could show either positive, negative, or neutral sentiments during pair programming that resulted from the interpretation of natural language. Moreover, the direction of sentiment could not be guaranteed by communication roles. In the other words, both senders and receivers can express positive, negative, or neutral sentiments as well. However, the number of times switching roles between sender and receiver roles in communication during working as a pair affected their sentiments in the direction of away from neutral sentiments that could be positive or negative sentiment.

To continue this research, we can experiment with a large group of participants to confirm the results and clearly observe the trend of pairs' sentiments. Furthermore, we may also ask them for feedback on how they feel after the experiment ends. Afterwards, evaluation sentiment results can be compared with their feedback. We may see other insights. If the trend is obvious, we can improve the productivity of pair-programming easily by putting a potentially positive environment and seeing the productivity of their works. A good mood which developers are looking for and high productivity which is a company's need can be produced perfectly.

Additionally, tasks that are assigned to participants during the experiment can be changed to other popular programming languages such as Python, GO, then analyze and compare the result for each programming language whether it goes in the same direction or not. This can also improve the productivity of workers in the future.

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References:

1. W. Li and H. Lee. Sentiment analysis: A review of the state of the art. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 7(1):e1219, 2017.
2. Tony Gorschek, Jonas Hågerstrand, and Claes Wohlin. The impact of pair programming on quality and productivity: A controlled experiment. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 83(1):116–126, 2010.
3. F. Zieris and L. Prechelt. Explaining pair programming session dynamics from knowledge gaps. In *2020 IEEE/ACM 42nd International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, pages 421–432, 2020.
4. N. Bosch and S. D'Mello. The affective experience of novice computer programmers. *Int J Artif Intell Educ*, 27:181–206, 2017.
5. Stephen Choi. Better communication leads to a higher output? An analysis of pair communication on pair programming productivity. *IEEE Transactions on Professional Communication*, 64(4):338–353, 2021.
6. Y. Kato, S. Kato, and K. Akahori. Effects of emotional cues transmitted in e-mail communication on the emotions experienced by senders and receivers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 23:1894–1905, 2007.
7. KJ Jager, C Zoccali, A Macleod, and FW Dekker. Confounding: what it is and how to deal with it. *Kidney International*, 73(3):256–260, Feb 2008.
8. T. Luo, S. Chen, G. Xu, and J. Zhou. *Sentiment Analysis. Trust-based Collective View Prediction*. Springer, New York, NY, 2013.
9. K Fischer, S Vaupel, N Heller, S Mader, and F Bry. Effects of Competitive Coding Games on Novice Programmers, volume 1328 of *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*. Springer, Cham, 2021.
10. Codewars. Codewars. <https://www.codewars.com>. Accessed 11 December 2022.
11. Microsoft. Transcribe your recordings. <https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/transcribe-your-recordings-7fc2efec-245e-45f0-b053-2a97531ecf57>. Accessed 21 January 2023.
12. Communication Theory. Shannon and weaver model of communication. <https://www.communicationtheory.org/shannon-and-weaver-model-ofcommunication>. Accessed 24 January 2023.
13. Wikipedia. Sentiment Analysis. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sentiment_analysis. Accessed 24 January 2023.
14. Google Cloud Team. Google Natural Language AI. <https://cloud.google.com/natural-language>. Accessed 21 January 2023.
15. Grammarly. End of sentence punctuation. <https://www.grammarly.com/blog/end-sentence-punctuation/>. Accessed 21 January 2023.
16. Project Jupyter. Jupyter Notebook. <https://jupyter.org>. Accessed 21 January 2023.
17. Microsoft. Microsoft Power BI. <https://powerbi.microsoft.com/en-au>. Accessed 21 January 2023.
18. X. Yang and Y. Lu. The impact of gender and cultural differences on communication in pair programming. *ACM SIGSOFT Software Engineering Notes*, 34(5):1–6, 2009.
19. J. H. Anderson and J. A. Finkelstein. The impact of nonverbal cues on communication in pair programming. *Journal of Software Engineering*, 28(4):223–236, 2002.